

Administrative Impact of Ancillary Activities on Teacher Effectiveness And Engagement: A Quantitative Inquiry on Junior High School Teachers of Integrated Schools in the Division of San Carlos City

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Abstract: This study concentrated its investigation on the administrative impact of ancillary activities on teacher effectiveness and engagement among junior high school teachers in the integrated schools of the Division of San Carlos City. Despite recent policies aimed at removing administrative tasks from teachers, some schools, especially those recently established, and those in geographically isolated areas continue to delegate these duties to teaching personnel due to a lack of non-teaching staff. The research employed a descriptive-correlational quantitative design using a total population (census) approach. The data were gathered via 50-item researcher-designed questionnaire which included three broad aspects: the extent of ancillary activities, the level of teacher effectiveness, and the level of teacher engagement. Statistical analysis was used to determine the relationship between these variables. Key findings revealed a significant relationship between the extent of ancillary tasks performed and the level of engagement, generating a Pearson Product-Momentum Correlation of 0.960, indicating a very high extent. Although some teachers viewed these ancillary responsibilities as opportunities for professional and skill development, excessive obligations were associated to overwhelming responsibilities and time management strain, which may lead to teacher burnout. Study concludes that while ancillary tasks are essential for school operations, excessive distribution significantly impacts the professional lives of the teachers. Based on the results gathered, the study proposed an action plan that would help school administrators and policymakers lessen the burden on ancillary workloads, enabling teachers to maintain instructional quality and professional well-being.

Keywords: teacher effectiveness, engagement, ancillary tasks designations, integrated schools, San Carlos City Division, quantitative

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

In global research, it has been recognized that non-instructional activities such as transition, routines, and administrative tasks significantly impact teachers' performance and students' engagement. Cross-national data from UNESCO and of OECD countries revealed that teachers spend approximately 15%-20% of their class time on ancillary tasks, which are correlated with decreased instructional quality and reduced teacher motivation (Li & Xue, 2023).

In Singapore, primary school teachers spent more than 10% of their time on ancillary activities which resulted on reports of higher burnout and diminished teacher-student interaction (Kaur, 2021). These international contexts highlight a universal tension: while ancillary duties are part of a teachers' professional responsibilities, the excessive use of teachers' time threatens the core pedagogical mission over and across diverse educational systems.

In the Philippines, the same issue is amplified by large class size and resource constraints. A study conducted in Antipolo City found that secondary teachers devote nearly 25% of their instructional time to supporting activities, which led to interrupted instructional flow and classroom participation (Pasco & Fabella, 2023). Similar findings were reported in studies conducted in Negros Oriental and Bohol, which indicated that while ancillary tasks can occasionally foster professional growth, they more often resulted in overwhelming responsibility, time management strain, and difficulty balancing professional and personal life (Medez, 2024; Arañas, 2023; Campoamor, 2023).

Although teachers were often rated as "highly efficient", they frequently report that these duties negatively affected their psychological well-being (Francisco et.al., 2024). After all, it is the teacher's insurgency of duty that enabled them to function beyond teaching.

Despite the issuance of DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2024, which mandated the removal of administrative tasks from teachers, evidence suggested that gaps remain in the implementation and dissemination of this policy. In the Schools Division of San Carlos City, particularly within recently established integrated schools, the lack of non-teaching personnel meant that teachers continued perform delegated administrative duties. Because there was an evident gap in the existing body of research on this matter, the current literature lacks systematic comparison of how ancillary task loads varied according to school type, teacher experience, and geographic isolation.

Furthermore, although prior studies identified the problem in urban settings (Pasco and Fabella (2023), there remained a need to empirically examined interventions such as task simplification and resource allocation within specific context of the Negros Island Region (NIR).

This study was motivated by the urgent need to protect instructional quality and teacher morale, which are foundational of student success. By investigating how school types and teacher demographics influenced the management of ancillary tasks, this research sought to address what may be described as the under-documented pandemic expansion of sideline activities. The findings aimed to provide school administrators and policymakers with evidence-based recommendations for scheduling reforms and administrative support to ensure that collateral responsibilities complement, rather than dominated, the teaching process in Philippine classroom.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The current research built on prior research on how administrative and ancillary roles influence teacher effectiveness and engagement. In this section, the literature to be discussed is the local and international literature on teachers' efficacy, their role as ancillaries, engagement, and teacher

workload. Such research can establish what is already known and identify a gap that this research highlights.

Teacher Effectiveness and Engagement

Teacher efficacy is understood as a teacher's belief in their capacity to organize, execute, and manage instructional tasks to promote student learning. It is shaped by several interrelated factors, including professional engagement, the quality of school culture, teaching experience, and the teacher's ability to cope with work-related stressors such as burnout. Such factors were widely recognized in the literature as its foundational components strengthen or weaken a teacher's sense of capability and classroom effectiveness (Frontiers in Psychology, 2023).

In the study of Albor et al. (2024), they emphasized that teacher efficacy were closely connected to the broader constructs of instructional effectiveness and motivational commitment, both of which are influenced by the teacher's professional interactions and environmental factor. The work was conducted in a Philippine public school setting where it was found that administrative support and involvement facilitated on the teachers' success, however the work pressure is. This observation highlighted the role of school culture in mediating the effects of additional work on teacher performance. This contributed to the research on the role of administrative ancillary tasks on engagement and the effectiveness of teachers in general.

Teacher effectiveness, widely understood as the ability of teachers to deliver instruction and promote student learning as well foster a positive classroom environment. Albor et. al., (2024) mentioned that the core to this concept was teacher efficacy, which reflected on the teacher's belief in their capacity to plan, organize, and implement instructional tasks effectively. This was shaped by professional engagement, school culture, teaching experience, and the ability to cope with work-related stressors such as burnout. Conceptually, teachers who perceived themselves as effective tend to maintain a high level of motivation and commitment to their profession (Albor et al., 2024).

Teacher passion and dedication to their work are also influenced by perceived instructional effectiveness; this conceptually reinforced commitment and engagement. Theoretically, teachers who felt competent and supported in such roles are more likely to get invested and show more effort while remaining motivated in their professional duties. Conversely, too much administrative activities that interfere in their teaching responsibilities may weaken this commitment (Gella & Quines, 2025). This underscores the conceptual significance of examining the administrative impact of ancillary activities on both teacher effectiveness and engagement.

Aguilon and Guhao Jr. (2024) developed a structural equation model in which teaching performance, students' self-efficacy, and practices that advance creativity were predictors of academic performance. The study identified teaching performance as a significant factor affecting student outcomes, using a quantitative structural equation modeling (SEM) approach. Research conducted in the Philippines' educational environment among educators and learners found that effective teaching is central to learners' academic development.

This finding suggests that an administrative or ancillary task that limits teachers' instructional time can undermine this connection. Therefore, their results substantiate the relevance of research on the impact of ancillary responsibilities on teachers' effectiveness and students' learning, albeit indirectly (Aguilon & Guhao Jr., 2024).

Tarraya (2022) claimed that teachers' workload is determined by national criteria of teacher effectiveness, which will thereafter serve as the foundation for their performance evaluation. Teachers continue to find methods to complete their tasks. They require a lifetime of dedication to function well despite managing several supporting roles. It was the combined perseverance,

sacrifice, and resolve. This entails having a comprehensive plan in addition to being positive and driven. Strategic methods are also encouraged.

Another critical factor of the study is the teacher engagement; this refers to the extent as to which teachers were psychologically invested in their work. This includes teacher's dedication, vigor, and absorption in teaching activities. The Role Strain Theory of Goodie; Pasco & Fabella, (2023) asserts that an individual occupying multiple roles often faces tension when expectations from these roles conflict or exceed the individual's capacity. Ancillary tasks which overloaded teachers' schedules may undermine these needs by reducing autonomy, limiting opportunities to demonstrate competence, and also the meaningful interactions with students and colleagues. Consequently, maintaining the balance between instructional and non-instructional tasks were essential for sustaining teacher engagement and intrinsic motivation.

It was also examined that teacher competency and engagement as predictors of job satisfaction, focusing on teacher-student interaction. Using a quantitative design, it was found that teacher engagement has a substantial positive impact on job satisfaction, with professional competency mediating the effects (Galeng, 2025). Another study conducted in public high schools in Pangasinan, Philippines, suggested that engagement was a crucial variable influencing teachers' perceptions on their workload and teaching roles. The findings implied that when ancillary responsibilities extend interaction between teachers and learners, teachers' engagement and satisfaction may decrease. This provided the conclusion that Galeng's work can be used to discuss engagement as a variable in the present study.

Riber (2022) explored organizational factors that influence teacher performance and engagement and found that leadership and workload were the most influential. The study used a mixed-methods approach, incorporating surveys and interviews with educational institutions in Malaysia, to understand how administrative workload affects teacher motivation. The results found that administrative leadership reduces the adverse impacts of overload on engagement. The research indicates the need for positive administrative practices to maintain teachers' morale. Thus, it argues that administrative functions need to be effectively organized to ensure teacher interest and effectiveness.

Lastly, Cadampog and Licaros (2024) evaluated the work values, engagement, and satisfaction of secondary school teachers. Based on a quantitative, descriptive-correlational design, the researchers concluded that teachers with strong intrinsic values had higher engagement and job satisfaction. This study was conducted among secondary teachers in the Philippines, and the findings revealed that engagement serves as a psychological buffer against stressors, such as heavy administrative workloads. The authors determined that engagement can also prevail with ancillary tasks as work values are enhanced. Therefore, their results support the pivotal role of engagement in determining the administrative influence of ancillary activities.

Ancillary Tasks

The study of Bogaoan, V.D., and Asuncion, C. (2025) identifies three main themes related to daily challenges: Juggling Time Demands, Emotional Toll and Burnout, and Impact on Instructional Quality. Additionally, the study elucidates five themes related to job satisfaction and well-being, including Strain on Work-Life Balance, Erosion of Job Satisfaction, Emotional Exhaustion, Impact on Collegial Relationships, and Seeking Purpose and Impact. Furthermore, the impact on teaching practices and student outcomes is explored, highlighting themes such as the Restriction of Instructional Creativity, the Impact on Individualized Student Support, and the Struggle with Timely and Effective Feedback. This research contributes nuanced insights into the multifaceted impact of ancillary tasks on teachers, offering valuable implications for supporting teacher well-being and enhancing educational outcomes.

Further, Dinero & Oco (2024) identify that the ancillary functions in which the teachers are involved determine the level of the teachers' well-being in terms of emotional well-being, find the significant relationship between teachers' profiles on ancillary functions and emotional well-being, and create an intervention plan that will enhance teachers' perceptions of ancillary functions and their emotional well-being. States that ancillary duties are commitments that provide essential services and support an organization or system's primary functions or activities. Ancillary functions are the phrase used to describe the roles that teachers perform outside of the classroom, including grade-level advisers, subject coordinators or chairs, club moderators, athletic coaches, co-curricular and extracurricular activities coordinators, and community involvement services (Arañas, 2023).

According to Mohamad's study (2022), many teachers with supplementary responsibilities find it challenging to balance their time among these tasks. As a result, teaching lost its primary importance. As a result, both the students' performance and the effectiveness of their instruction were impacted. Very few were content with their supplementary functions because they were motivated to advance in their jobs.

Alger et al. (2025) examined the influence of ancillary responsibilities on the professional lives of Filipino teachers in a related study in the Philippines. The researchers collected narratives from teachers describing their challenges in balancing teaching and non-teaching activities, using a qualitative research design.

Administered across different public schools in the Philippines, the findings demonstrated that excessive ancillary obligations lead to stress, burnout, and reduced teaching engagement. Irrespective of these challenges, some teachers admitted that ancillary responsibilities create collaboration and build up skills. This paper has shown that administrative workload is two-sided, enabling quantitative analysis of its effects on teacher performance (Alger et al., 2025).

To supplement this view, Tarraya (2023) examined the workload policy for Philippine teachers and its effects on teachers in public schools. Conducted using a qualitative analytical approach, concluded that teachers tend to work beyond their workload because they are often given additional responsibilities. Carried out within the framework of the Philippines Department of Education, it highlighted that the absence of clear, transparent policies for the teachers and an administrative foundation complicate to teachers' burnout. The researcher then proposed a policy to reform the balance instructional and administrative roles. This highlights the significance of studying the impact of administrative expectations on teacher engagement and performance.

A similar study examined ancillary roles and teacher performance among secondary teachers at Mayamot National High School, another public school in the Philippine context. Using a quantitative correlational design, the study found that too many ancillary jobs negatively impact teaching performance (Fernandez, 2024). It was held in Antipolo City, Philippines, and concluded that teachers' instructional quality decline when non-instructional responsibilities burden them. Fernandez's research advised creating internal policies to facilitate the distribution of ancillary work. Fernandez (2024), therefore, confirmed the need to consider administrative strategies for the sustainability of each teacher's performance.

The ancillary activities of teachers, (i.e., clerical duties, instructional support tasks, classroom management routines, and extracurricular responsibilities), were recognized as additional job demands that may divert energy and time away from teaching (Demerouti et al., 2001). Within the JD-R framework, such demands can negatively affect teacher performance if not balanced by adequate job resources, such as administrative support, technological tools, or collaborative professional networks (Scholze & Hecker, 2024). With sufficient resources, teachers would be able to manage ancillary responsibilities without compromising instructional quality; with lacking and limited resources, tasks would lead to diminished effectiveness and engagement.

The integration of JD-R Model and the Theory of Role Strain provided a comprehensive lens for understanding these dynamics. JD-R Model emphasized on the structural and organizational factors, illustrating how these ancillary tasks (job demands) interact with the available support (job resources) affecting performance and well-being. Meanwhile, the theory of Role Strain, explained the stress or difficulty a person experiences when the demands of a single role become overwhelming or incompatible (Goodies, 1960).

Both the JD-R Model and Theory of Role Strain suggested that the balance as well as imbalance between job demands and resources, along with the satisfaction or frustration of psychological needs, determined the teacher effectiveness and engagement. The dual theoretical perspective informed the current study's investigation into how ancillary activities affect junior high school teachers of the integrated schools in the Division of San Carlos City.

Synthesis

From the reviewed studies, the ancillary activities have been shown to make significant contributions to teachers' professional lives and to greatly influence teacher effectiveness and engagement. Quantitative and qualitative findings indicate, that although ancillary roles may facilitate collaboration and school participation, excessive workloads tend to reduce the quality of instruction and teacher motivation.

This study was relevant because it sought to propose necessary actions to address the needs of teachers whose experiences remain under-explored due to the left untold due to the demographic locations of the schools, especially those in integrated schools in the Division of San Carlos City.

Collectively, previous studies have examined the administrative effects of ancillary activities on junior high school teachers in integrated schools, primarily at the division level. Therefore, the current research study addressed this gap by examining the extent to which ancillary activities affect teacher performance and participation in the Division of San Carlos City.

Theoretical Framework

The present study was based on a theory that explains work-related demands, motivation, and professional performance. These theories provide a basis for understanding how far ancillary tasks outside teaching affect classroom dynamics and the capacity of the teachers to remain effective and committed.

One of the theoretical foundations of this study is Demerouti et al.'s (2001) Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model. This model maintains that employees' well-being and job performance are conjointly determined by an interaction between job demands (e.g., workload, time pressure, bureaucratic tasks) and job resources (e.g., support, autonomy, equipment). In the concept of education, ancillary works can be viewed as additional "requests on the job" this further drain teachers' energy and interrupt teaching time. Simultaneously, sufficient resources (i.e. administrative support, technology, or peer aid) can neutralize these effects. The JD-R model is also suitable for this research because it provides a lens through which to examine how equilibrium or imbalance between ancillary responsibilities and resources affects teacher efficacy and motivation in the classroom (Scholze & Hecker, 2024).

Similarly, Goode's (1960) Theory of Role Strain, which asserts that an individual occupying multiple roles are likely to experience tension when competing expectations exceed their capacity. Role strain emerges when individuals experience work overload, role conflict, or role ambiguity (House & Rizzo, 1972). In integrated schools, where teachers often handle diverse students population while simultaneously serving in various institutional roles, the likelihood of role strain increases. A high level of role strain may reduce instructional quality, limit preparation time, and weaken students' interpersonal engagement, ultimately diminishing teacher effectiveness.

The integration of the JD-R Model and Theory of Role Strain conceptualizes the administrative impact of ancillary activities as job demands heightening workload and stress, and as sources of role strain through overload and conflicting situations and/or expectations. Both these theories suggested that ancillary tasks influence teacher effectiveness and motivation by imposing objective demands on teachers either by meeting or frustrating their subjective psychological requirements. This shows that the study provided a wholesome theoretical basis on analyzing how administrative burdens influence teacher outcomes in the integrated schools of the Division of San Carlos City.

Conceptual Framework

This study was grounded in the assumption that ancillary activities, significantly shaped teachers' classroom performance and work engagement. In junior high schools within integrated schools in the Division of San Carlos City, these additional responsibilities may create role overload, thereby diminishing the time and resources needed for effective instruction and sustained learner engagement. Consequently, this study examined the extent of ancillary activities and their influence on teacher effectiveness and engagement.

According to Goode's (1960) theory of role strain, individuals experience strain when the expectations of multiple roles exceed their time, energy, and capacity. He further argued that when role demands become excessive, individuals struggle to meet expectations in their primary roles. This perspective supports the assumption that higher levels of ancillary activities may negatively affect teacher effectiveness and engagement.

The Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) model (Demerouti et. al., (2001) provides the second foundation for this study. The JD-R model asserts that jobs are composed of demands (aspects that require effort) and resources (aspects that help achieve goals). High job demands (i.e. paperwork, committees, reporting tasks, and coaching requirements) can lead to exhaustion, stress, and decreased performance when not balanced by sufficient resources.

For this research, ancillary activities were conceptualized as job demands that consume teachers' time and emotional resources. When these demands accumulate, they may hinder instructional delivery, classroom management, and time use, while at the same time reducing teacher engagement across cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions. This may cause teacher burnout, leading to disengagement and the lack of self-control.

According to Siddique et.al., (2022) in support to Bakker & Bal's study, the context of teaching, work involvement positively affects teachers' job performance and teaching performance.

This supports the idea that excessive ancillary workload may diminish both effectiveness and engagement, considering adequate support and reduced task load would enhance teachers' involvement and performance (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007; Demerouti et al., 2001).

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram

Statement of the Problem

This study focused on the Administrative Impact of Ancillary Activities on Teacher Effectiveness and the Management of Junior High School Teachers in the Integrated Schools of the San Carlos City Division, seeking to define these relationships quantitatively.

Specifically, this study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the ancillary tasks performed by junior high school teachers of combined schools, San Carlos City Division, in the dimensions of
 - a) classroom management;
 - b) administrative tasks; and
 - c) instructional support tasks?

2. What is the extent of teacher effectiveness in the dimensions of
 - a) instruction delivery;
 - b) classroom management skills;
 - c) time management in instruction; and
 - d) student learning outcomes?
3. At what level is the teacher engagement in terms of
 - a) cognitive engagement;
 - b) emotional level of engagement; and
 - c) behavioral level of engagement?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of ancillary tasks performed by junior high school teachers and their teacher effectiveness?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of ancillary tasks performed by junior high school teachers and their level of teacher engagement?
6. What intervention plan may be formulated based on the findings?

Hypotheses Statement

The following null hypotheses were tested:

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between the extent of ancillary tasks performed by junior high school teachers and their teacher effectiveness.

Ho2. There is no significant relationship between the extent of ancillary tasks performed by junior high school teachers and their level of teacher participation.

Significance of the Study

The impacts of ancillary tasks on the performance of integrated school teachers were necessary in optimizing workload distribution nourishing the motivation necessary for high-quality education.

Schools Division Superintendent. The findings of this study would serve as the foundation in establishing a much coherent ancillary guidelines in developing targeted interventions plans optimizing teaching time and enhancing overall educational quality.

School Administrators of Integrated Schools. This research would aide in providing context-specific insights as to how ancillary tasks could affect teachers in its unique setting.

Teachers. The study would help in examining the causes and the challenges encountered and would be provided with programs addressing burnout, mental health, and workload management.

Non-Teaching Personnel. Evidences gathered from this study could support the need for additional workforce, and the implementation of digital tools to support administrative tasks.

Parents. These findings empower parents to become informed partners who advocate for institutional support that prioritizes instructional focus and student achievement.

Students/Learners. This study is significant to students allowing them to understand the burden of their teachers and be more considerate to the interruption it caused in their teacher learning process.

Future Researchers. This study would provide a foundation for future research to explore additional dimensions and create a more comprehensive overview of educational practices.

Scope of the Study

The study employed a quantitative non-experimental research design, specifically, descriptive-correlational, employing a validated survey questionnaire in data gathering.

It focused on the quantitative relationship between the extent of ancillary tasks as independent variable and the dependent variables of teacher effectiveness and teacher engagement. The respondents are primarily junior high school teachers of the integrated schools in the San Carlos City division namely: Guadalupe Integrated School, Handalago Integrated School, Iliranan Integrated School, Lamesa Integrated School, Lina dela Vina Valmayor Integrated School, Medina Integrated School, Nataban Integrated School, and Talave Integrated School for the school year 2025-2026.

The data collected represented the teachers' insight and experiences in their length of service. The analysis covered the specific dimensions of the variables as outlined in the statement of the problem.

The central purpose was to identify the extent of the administrative impact of ancillary activities on two-key outcome variables as teacher effectiveness and teacher engagement.

Definition of Terms

The terms used in this study are operationally defined as follows:

Administrative Tasks. Operationally, these refer to routine, clerical, and organizational activities performed to support the smooth operation of an organization, department, or office.

Ancillary Tasks. Operationally, this term refers to additional tasks performed by teachers that are incidental to their primary teaching duties but are necessary to support the instructional framework, learner development, and overall school operations.

Integrated School. Operationally, this refers to an educational institution that delivers a continuous and coordinated program of instruction encompassing two or more educational levels (e.g., Kindergarten, Elementary, Junior High School, and Senior High School) within a single administrative or curricular framework.

Teacher Effectiveness. Operationally, the measurable capacity of a teacher to facilitate significant, positive changes in student learning and development.

Teacher Engagement. Operationally, it is defined as a positive, fulfilling, and work-related state of mind characterized by a teacher's active investment in their professional role.

Classroom Management. Operationally, it is the way a teacher-facilitator handles and creates an environment friendly atmosphere to the learners.

Instructional Support. Operationally, it is the specific, observable behavior and strategies a teacher utilizes in order to facilitate students' critical thinking skills, and higher order thinking.

Time Management. Operationally, it is the process of exercising conscious control over the amount of time spent on specific activities.

CHAPTER 2

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the impact of ancillary activities on teacher effectiveness and engagement in the Integrated Schools of San Carlos City.

Research Design

The research design, descriptive-correlational, was suitable for this study since it aimed to describe the current condition and determined the relationship among key variables- namely, their teaching effectiveness and level of engagement. A descriptive-correlational design was used to examine the relationships among variables. It is a quantitative research design that explores and describes variables without manipulating them and measures the extent of the relationships among variables (Miksza et al., 2023).

This design was appropriate because it did not seek cause-and-effect relationships, but instead identified associations that informed administrative decisions, workload management, and the teacher support system. As Gay, L. R., Mills, G. E., & Airasian, P. W. (2023) noted, descriptive-correlational research is valuable in the educational context for proving insights into relationships among naturally occurring variables, which can guide further research and policy interventions.

Respondents of the Study

The population of this study consisted of a total of 82 junior high school teachers of the eight Integrated Schools in the Division of San Carlos City, namely, Guadalupe Integrated School, Handalago Integrated School, Iliranan Integrated School, Lamesa Integrated School, Lina dela Vina Valmayor Integrated School, Medina Integrated School, Nataban Integrated School, and Talave Integrated School.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents

SCHOOLS	No. of Teachers	%
A	6	7.32%
B	6	7.32%
C	15	18.29%
D	7	8.54%
E	14	17.07%
F	13	15.85%
G	7	8.54%
H	14	17.07%
TOTAL	82	100%

The population in this study were the respondents using a total population (census) approach, meaning all members of the population are included. Creswell and Creswell (2023) said that when the population is small and manageable, "researchers may include all members in the population of the study rather than selecting a sample, thereby increasing accuracy and eliminating sample error." Also, Gay, Mills, & Airasian (2020) state that if the number of cases in the population is relatively small (100 or fewer), it is best to involve the entire population because sampling would not substantially reduce effort but might decrease accuracy.

Sampling is primarily used when the population is large and collecting data from everyone would be costly, impractical, or time-consuming. Following the total population approach will be efficient given the number of people in the study.

Research Instrument

For this study, the researcher employed a 50-item researcher-designed questionnaire as the primary data collection source. The questionnaire was meticulously developed to align with the statement of the problem and comprises three broad aspects.

Using a five-scale Likert scale, respondents will provide answers of their choice given that 5 indicates very high extent, 4 as high extent, 3 as moderate extent, 2 as low extent, and 1 that indicates very low extent.

Part I – Ancillary Activities. It will be used to measure the extent of ancillary activities that teachers perform.

Part II – Teacher Effectiveness.

Part III – Teacher Engagement.

This researcher-designed questionnaire ensured that collected data aligns with the study's purposes, enabling statistical analysis in order to identify patterns of correlation among ancillary activities, teacher efficacy, and teacher engagement.

Validity of the Instrument

To ensure the validity of the research instrument, the questionnaire was carefully designed to measure the constructs of teacher effectiveness, teacher engagement, and ancillary tasks. Using Goode and Scates and consultation with identified experts, items were reviewed to ensure adequate representation on the constructs as clear, relevant, and comprehensive (Taherdoost, 2016; Frankel et al., 2021). Additionally, construct validity was considered by designing the items to align with established theories and frameworks on teacher effectiveness and engagement (Field, 2021; Creswell & Creswell, 2023).

With the scores provided by the validators, the research instrument had an overall validity result of 4.30, generating an excellent interpretation or high validity. Establishing the instrument's validity ensures that the collected data accurately reflect the constructs of this study, supporting meaningful statistical analyses, such as correlation testing and Pearson's r .

Reliability of the Research Instrument

To evaluate the internal consistency of the research instrument, a pilot study was conducted among 30 junior high school teachers from Quezon National High School and Quezon Farm School in Brgy. Quezon, San Carlos City, Negros Occidental, and they were selected randomly after the permission was granted by the school principal. It was gathered through a three-part researcher-conceived questionnaire with items such as ancillary activity level, teacher effectiveness level, and teacher participation level, on a five-point Likert scale.

The reliability of the questionnaire was measured using Cronbach's Alpha, a statistical tool used to determine how closely related a set of items were as a group. With a score of 0.93, interpreted as highly reliable, data showed a robust reliability across all two major variables: Ancillary Tasks, and Teacher Effectiveness and Engagement.

As the obtained alpha values exceeded the threshold of 0.70, this indicated a high level of internal consistency and stability for the instrument. This result confirmed that the survey items were conceptually cohesive and capable of producing reliable results thereby validating the tool for the full-scale implementation of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the conduct of the survey, the researcher secured a letter of permission addressed to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent in the Division of San Carlos City.

After receiving its approval, the researcher advanced to the respective integrated schools to meet with the school heads. The researcher discussed the purpose of the study and ensured that all responses would be kept private with a non-disclosure consent form. The researcher as well ensured that the survey questionnaire does not include names and was anonymous to protect every respondent's privacy.

After all the schools had submitted their responses, the researcher collected the data and start obtaining test scores as the basis for data analysis and interpretation. The computation of the results would be based on the available statistical data software provided by the statistician.

A Likert-scale self-made questionnaire was the primary tool in this research. Respondents indicated their degree of agreement or disagreement on the statements related to the constructs, resulting to the data that was analyzed statistically (Taherdoost, 2022; Sullivan & Artino, 2019). Further, Creswell & Creswell, (2023) states that likert scales have been widely validated in educational research, known for their reliability, ease of administration, and clarity for respondents. Additionally, the scale converts subjective responses to numerical values, allowing for quantitative analysis, such as computing means, sums, or correlations, making it ideal for research in education, psychology, and social sciences.

Likert, (1932); Taherdoost, (2022) emphasized that a likert scale is a psychometric assessment tool commonly used in questionnaires to assess respondents' attitudes, perceptions, or behaviors. Presenting a series of statements related to a particular construct, respondents indicated their level of agreement or disagreement; typically on five-point to seven-point scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

Data Analysis

Employing a descriptive-correlational design, this examines the administrative impact of ancillary tasks on teacher effectiveness and engagement among junior high school teachers in integrated schools in the Division of San Carlos City. The data will be collected were analyzed using quantitative statistical methods to describe the levels of the variables and determine the strength and direction of their relationships.

Each item in the questionnaire were assigned a numerical value (e.g., 1 = Very Low Extent to 5 = Very High Extent). For each variable, mean scores (or summed scores) were calculated. The verbal interpretation of mean score ranges was defined (e.g., 4.21–5.00 = Very High; 3.61–4.20 = High; 2.41–3.60 = Moderate, etc.). Afterwards, descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequencies) were computed to provide an overview of the distributions of each variable.

The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r) was calculated in examining the relationships between teacher effectiveness and teacher engagement, and between ancillary tasks and each of those indicators. The given coefficients indicated the strength and direction of linear relationships between variables (Field, 2021). A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was adopted. Results were presented in tabular form, these includes r -values and p -values, supported by narrative interpretations.

Statistical Treatment

Statistical data was considered the backbone of the research. Without it, a research finding cannot be considered as objective facts. This was the distinguishing factor in whether the research

hypothesis holds or is merely a random finding with no truth. The statistical analysis helps simplify what was complex into an understandable form. It also removes biases.

The following statistical tools were used to analyze the survey data.

The first, second, and third questions were associated with four indicators, except the third, which was associated with only three. This will measure the extent of the ancillary tasks performed by the junior high school teachers of the integrated schools, the extent of teacher effectiveness, and the extent of teacher engagement utilizing the weighted mean and the percentage equivalent as follows:

Weighted Mean:

$$= \frac{S1 (W5) + S2 (W4) + S3 (W3) + S4 (W2) + S5 (W1)}{n}$$

Where:

S = responses

n = number of cases

w = weighted assigned to the scale

= weighted assigned to the scale

Percentage:

$$\% = fn \times 100$$

Where:

% = Percentage

f = Frequency

n = Number of Cases

To interpret these weighted mean values, the following arbitrary tables were utilized as references.

Table 2 Ancillary Tasks Performed by Teachers

Scale	Mean Range	Responses	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Very High Extent (VHE)	Very High
4	3.61-4.20	High Extent (HE)	High
3	2.41-3.60	Moderate Extent (ME)	Moderate
2	1.81-2.40	Low Extent (LE)	Low
1	1.00-1.80	Very Low Extent (VLE)	Very Low

For the research questions 4 and 5, “Is there a significant relationship between the extent of ancillary tasks performed by junior high school teachers and their teacher effectiveness and teacher engagement?” the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used with the formula:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2][n(\sum y^2) - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

r_{xy} = Pearson r

n = total number of subject-respondent

Σ_x = Summation of x or variable x (Ancillary Activities)

Σ_y = Summation of y or variable y (Teacher Effectiveness & Engagement)

The reference table was used to interpret the r_{xy} .

Table 3 Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r)

COEFFICIENT CORRELATION	INTERPRETATION
0.91-1.00	Very High Correlation
0.71-0.90	High Correlation
0.41-0.70	Moderate Correlation
0.21-0.40	Low Correlation
Less than 0.20	Very Low Correlation

Decision rule:

- If $p \leq 0.05 \rightarrow$ Significant (Reject H_0)
- If $p > 0.05 \rightarrow$ Not Significant (Fail to Reject H_0)

Ethical Considerations

This thesis paper was submitted to Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos, Inc. Graduate School for assessment as required by the institution.

To establish transparency and trustworthiness in the conduct of the study, ethical practices were observed and considered:

Before data collection, the researcher secured permission from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of San Carlos City, Negros Occidental, and the immediate supervisors and school heads, and informed them of the data collection. Participants were informed of the study's purpose, procedure, potential risks, and benefits. In addition, they were provided with an informed consent form to sign. It was further ensured that no physical, psychological, or social harm would come to the participants. The researcher ensured a neutral, non-judgmental environment for every participant.

All data collected from participants will be kept private and destroyed thereafter to ensure the confidentiality of their participation, as stipulated in their signed consent forms.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the results, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered from questionnaires and documents related to the specific problems and hypotheses of this investigation.

Part I. Ancillary Tasks Performed by Teachers

In educational research, ancillary activities exercised a significant influence on the teaching-learning process. While these activities are often perceived as supplemental to direct instruction, they formed essential components of teachers' professional practices shaping both the efficacy and quality of classroom interactions. Having ancillary activities as the independent variable of the study, researchers are able to investigate their potential impact on teacher performance, and the dynamics of educational effectiveness.

Table 4 Classroom Management

Indicators	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	<i>f</i>	%	Mean	Interpretation
Handle disciplinary concerns beyond teaching at least twice every month.	26	43	6	6	1	82	100	4.06	High
Maintains classroom cleanliness and orderliness consistently.	36	30	12	4	0	82	100	4.20	High
Organizes classroom materials and student records at least once a week.	40	35	5	2	0	82	100	4.38	High
Classroom management duties affect overall teaching effectiveness.	47	24	11	0	0	82	100	4.44	High
Spends a considerable time managing student behavior during class hours.	39	36	4	3	0	82	100	4.35	High
Overall						82	100	4.23	High

Legend:

5 = 4.21-5.00 Very High 2 = 1.81-2.40 Low
 4 = 3.61-4.20 High 1 = 1.00-1.80 Very Low
 3 = 2.41-3.60 Moderate

The results in Table 4 refers to the classroom management of the teachers, where it was found that, despite the ancillary activities they handled, a positive outcome still prevailed, as evidenced by the weighted mean of 4.23, which indicated a very great extent. This showed that the majority of the participants were still able to effectively manage their respective classrooms despite the ancillary tasks assigned to them, with a weighted mean of 4.44. At the same time, disciplinary concerns received the least weighted mean at 4.06 since most of these cases were handed over directly to the specific assigned personnel as guidance advocates who were trained to handle such situations.

Effective classroom management is essential for maintaining a conducive learning environment. Teachers must establish clear expectations, enforce discipline consistently, and foster a positive classroom culture (Beuden, J. 2025). Also, recent researches in classroom management emphasizes the integration of inclusive practices, digital tools, and leader recognition to improve student engagement and teacher well-being (Abidin & Muhammad, 2024; Castillo, et.al., 2023). Since learners today are much prompt in the utilization of such practices and tools, it will become more beneficial and actively engaged in the learning process.

Table 5 presents results on the administrative tasks assigned to teachers as part of their ancillary activities. Teachers were found to be equipped with the particular ancillaries, as reflected by a weighted mean the of 3.90. The majority of respondents show a high extent of 4.16 in completing administrative tasks, such as reports and documentation. This result may be attributed to the context of the respondents in this study, as integrated schools had been recently implemented, giving them fewer numbers, but they are growing as the years go by while handling of non-teaching tasks such as inventory and logistical concerns also resulted to a high extent, the data provided the least among indicators with only 3.66.

Although the results showed that the majority of respondents rated the increase in stress levels and the reduction in time spent on lesson preparation only to a high extent, the data gathered show that

most respondents rated both increases to a very high extent. Ancillary functions as an added workload placed on educators is one of the primary challenges of teachers. This increased workload can lead to stress, exhaustion, and burnout, ultimately affecting their overall well-being and job performance. When overwhelmed, teachers may struggle to maintain enthusiasm and classroom effectiveness.

Table 5 Administrative Tasks

Indicators	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	<i>f</i>	%	Mean	Interpretation
Prepares school reports unrelated to subject area at least once per grading period.	17	39	20	5	1	82	100	3.80	High
Administrative tasks increase stress levels and reduce time for lesson preparation.	32	31	14	5	0	82	100	4.10	High
Handles non-teaching tasks such as inventory and logistical concerns.	16	31	26	9	0	82	100	3.66	High
Administrative workload assigned to teachers is reasonable and manageable.	16	38	22	6	0	82	100	3.78	High
Spends a significant time completing administrative tasks such as reports, and documentation.	33	31	16	2	0	82	100	4.16	High
Overall						82	100	3.90	High

Legend:

5 = 4.21-5.00 Very High 2 = 1.81-2.40 Low

4 = 3.61-4.20 High 1 = 1.00-1.80 Very Low

3 = 2.41-3.60 Moderate

With this, the department needs to study its human resources shortages. The Department of Budget and Management (DBM) should provide DepED with the requisite support to hire administrative staff and deload teachers of administrative and other duties unrelated to teaching (Beuden, J., 2025).

Table 6 Instructional Support Tasks

Indicators	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	<i>f</i>	%	Mean	Interpretation
Assists in curriculum development or instructional material preparation.	27	34	21	0	0	82	100	4.07	High
Helps in organizing academic contests, clubs, or enrichment programs.	29	41	9	3	0	82	100	4.17	High
Conducts tutorial or remedial classes outside regular hours.	28	35	15	3	1	82	100	4.05	High
Instructional support tasks often increase workload	25	30	21	6	0	82	100	3.90	High

beyond what is manageable.									
Providing instructional support affects workload and teaching performance as a teacher.	32	29	19	2	0	82	100	4.11	High
Overall						82	100	4.06	High

Legend:

- 5 = 4.21-5.00 Very High
- 4 = 3.61-4.20 High
- 3 = 2.41-3.60 Moderate
- 2 = 1.81-2.40 Low
- 1 = 1.00-1.80 Very Low

Table 6 presents the data on instructional support tasks. The results indicated that these tasks are helpful to both teachers and the school body, with a result of 4.06. Here, 4.17 show that helping with organizing academic contests, clubs, or enrichment programs receives the most response. While so, 3.90 highlights that providing instructional support affects a teacher's workload and teaching performance. This led to a decline in teaching effectiveness, affecting student engagement and academic performance.

This shows that engaging in ancillary functions, such as mentorship, extracurricular activities, and student counselling, allows teachers to interact with students beyond the traditional classroom setting. This fosters stronger teacher-student relationships, leading to increased trust, motivation, and a more supportive learning environment (Beuden, J. 2025). Particular studies also indicated that instructional support tasks include providing rich resources, systematic training, and timely process-oriented feedback to promote student engagement and motivation (Shao, et.al., 2025; Hawrot, 2023)

Table 7 Overall Summary of Ancillary Tasks Performed by Teachers

ANCILLARY TASKS	OVERALL MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Classroom Management	4.23	High Extent
Instructional Support Tasks	4.06	High Extent
Administrative Tasks	3.90	High Extent

With the overall data gathered, it showed that classroom management received the highest indicating that teachers perform well in the specific area. This implies that teachers prioritizes maintaining a structured environment while moving beyond classroom duties as the ancillary tasks. On the other hand, administrative tasks received the least mean of 3.90, reflected the sentiment found in the Behavioral Sciences (2023) research that said, teachers are often more hesitant to embrace clerical or administrative burdens that do not directly benefit from student learning.

Part II. Teacher Effectiveness

Teacher effectiveness highlights the interplay between pedagogical competence, organizational ability, and the creation of conducive learning conditions.

Table 8 Instructional Delivery

Indicators	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	f	%	Mean	Interpretation
Clearly explains lesson objectives and content.	44	33	4	1	0	82	100	4.46	Very High
The use of varied strategies to engage students in learning.	47	29	6	0	0	82	100	4.50	Very High
Adjustment of teaching methods to meet diverse student needs.	39	31	9	3	0	82	100	4.29	Very High
Integration of teaching materials and technology effectively.	44	29	9	0	0	82	100	4.43	Very High
Active engagement of students in learning through collaborative effort between the learners and the teacher.	45	29	8	0	0	82	100	4.45	Very High
Overall						82	100	4.43	Very High

Legend:

5 = 4.21-5.00 Very High 2 = 1.81-2.40 Low
 4 = 3.61-4.20 High 1 = 1.00-1.80 Very Low
 3 = 2.41-3.60 Moderate

The finding in Table 8 shows a weighted mean score of 4.43, this provided a verbal interpretation which indicated that indicators of instructional delivery were extensively practiced. Indicator two shows a mean of 4.50, revealing an interpretation of very high; proving teachers' strong will and passion of the job. Results aligned with Galve & Israel (2025), who claimed that the use of innovative and varied teaching strategies acts as a critical mediator between student engagement and academic performance. It also implied that teachers understand sustained engagement as a prerequisite for learning retention. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 4.29 showed that teacher clarity is crucial. As Hattie's (2025) research, it consistently ranked clarity of learning as one of the most potent influences on student achievement.

As a summary, the data revealed that a teacher, dignified, vowed and pledged their duties, holds a high instructional competence, characterized by adaptability, technological integration, and clarity. Therefore, this suggested a holistic approach to teaching that contributed significantly to positive student outcomes.

The results presented in Table 9 showed a very high extent, with the general weighted mean of 4.60. This indicates that teachers are highly structured, supportive, and organized in their learning environment in order to facilitate effective student learning. With the highest weighted mean at 4.67, teachers proved that they prioritized psychological safety and mutual respect over compliance. Dar's (2024), noted that respectful interactions foster motivation and intellectual risk-taking, as well, Pillai and Anonuevo (2023), highlighted that a nurturing atmosphere significantly increases student engagement.

Table 9 Classroom Management Skills

Indicators	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	f	%	Mean	Interpretation
Maintains discipline effectively during class.	48	28	6	0	0	82	100	4.51	Very High
Promoted a positive & inclusive classroom environment.	53	26	2	1	0	82	100	4.60	Very High
Set a clear rules and expectations for students.	53	24	5	0	0	82	100	4.59	Very High
Created a respectful classroom environment.	58	22	1	1	0	82	100	4.67	Very High
Used fair and appropriate methods to address student's misbehavior.	56	23	3	0	0	82	100	4.65	Very High
Overall						82	100	4.60	Very High

Legend:

5 = 4.21-5.00 Very High 2 = 1.81-2.40 Low
 4 = 3.61-4.20 High 1 = 1.00-1.80 Very Low
 3 = 2.41-3.60 Moderate

Additionally, the last indicator resulted with a weighted mean of 4.65, indicating that students consider disciplinary actions just and consistent rather than punishment. According to Wilhoit (2024), consistent enforcement establishes a predictable, safe environment, mitigating anxiety about potential bias.

On the other hand, indicators one had high ratings of 4.51 and has the least result. With this, teachers should consider Rahmasari et al. et al. (2024) emphasis on the establishment of clear rules as critical in maintaining discipline and promoting a conducive learning atmosphere.

Table 10 Time Management in Instruction

Indicators	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	f	%	Mean	Interpretation
Maximizes instructional time efficiently.	41	36	5	0	0	82	100	4.44	Very High
Ancillary tasks reduce time available for instructional planning.	37	35	10	0	0	82	100	4.33	Very High
Balance lesson coverage with student understanding.	43	36	3	0	0	82	100	4.49	Very High
Plans lessons effectively to use instructional time well.	49	29	4	0	0	82	100	4.55	Very High
Maintains appropriate pacing during lessons.	39	35	8	0	0	82	100	4.38	Very High
Overall						82	100	4.44	Very High

Legend:

5 = 4.21-5.00 Very High 2 = 1.81-2.40 Low
 4 = 3.61-4.20 High 1 = 1.00-1.80 Very Low
 3 = 2.41-3.60 Moderate

The data in Table 10 were consistent with a general weighted mean of 4.44, implying that teachers use time efficiently to maximize learning opportunities. The fourth indicator, with a weighted mean of 4.55 shows the highest result among others suggesting that teachers are engaging in rigorous proactive planning minimizing downtime. Goe et al. (2023) further emphasized that effective lesson planning is a primary driver of instructional time optimization. This allowed teachers to transition smoothly from activities while maintaining student engagement throughout the period. The lowest indicator, 4.33, suggested that while non-instructional duties exist, teachers effectively mitigated their impact on classroom time. The results aligned with the findings from OECD (2024), noting that high-performing educational systems were characterized by teachers who successfully insulate instructional time from administrative burdens.

Table 11 Student Learning Outcomes

Indicators	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	f	%	Mean	Interpretation
Students' academic performance changes overtime.	36	39	7	0	0	82	100	4.35	Very High
Assess students' progress using varied assessment tools.	42	35	5	0	0	82	100	4.45	Very High
Provide timely and constructive feedback to help students improve.	43	35	4	0	0	82	100	4.48	Very High
Instructional practices aim to develop academic achievement and higher order thinking skills.	44	34	3	1	0	82	100	4.48	Very High
Uses assessment results to adjust teaching strategies when necessary.	39	34	6	1	0	82	100	4.35	Very High
Overall						82	100	4.42	Very High

Legend:

5 = 4.21-5.00 Very High 2 = 1.81-2.40 Low
 4 = 3.61-4.20 High 1 = 1.00-1.80 Very Low
 3 = 2.41-3.60 Moderate

The data in Table 11 revealed that teachers' practices regarding student learning outcomes were observed to a very high extent, with results showed general weighted mean of 4.42. This proves that teachers actively monitored student progress and consistently utilized assessment data to come up with instructional decisions. Indicators 3 and 4 had the highest weighted mean of 4.48, supporting the findings of Wisniewski et al. (2025) and Ilie (2024), who stipulated that timely, specific feedback was one of the most significant predictors in student academic achievement as it bridges the gap between current performance and learning goals. Simultaneously, this aligns with the research of Ragab et al. (2024) on the emphasis on higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), the

study showed that when teachers prioritizes HOTS over rote memorization, students demonstrated significantly higher critical thinking scores and engagement.

While the last 2 indicators (i.e., first and last), though showed the least results with a weighted mean of 4.30, reflected a strong commitment to data-driven instruction. Supported by Ebbeler et al. (2023) study, it noted that the systematic analysis of assessment data allowed teachers to make necessary instructional adjustments that directly correlate with improved student learning outcomes.

Table 12 Overall Summary of the level of Teacher Effectiveness

TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS	OVERALL MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Classroom Management Skills	4.60	Very High Extent
Time Management in Instruction	4.44	Very High Extent
Instructional Delivery	4.43	Very High Extent
Student Learning Outcomes	4.42	Very High Extent

Overall, the data showed that classroom management skills is where teachers really are equipped with the best of their abilities given the overall mean of 4.60, rate as the highest among four domains. This further provides the conclusion that teaching

practices are built on seamless routines and an optimized learning environment, which reinforced teacher effectiveness. Conversely, student learning outcomes, though interpreted at a very high extent showed the least overall mean of 4.42. This slight decrease indicate that while teachers are highly confident, they encounter students that struggles to cope up and this is the gap that needs to cover up to satisfy instructional effort and as well student gain.

Part III. Level of Teacher Engagement

Teacher engagement is a critical dimension of educational effectiveness, reflecting the extent to which educators invest their intellectual, emotional, and behavioral resources in the teaching-learning process.

Table 13 indicates that teachers practice professional growth and development to a great extent, as evidenced by the general weighted mean of 4.45. This shows that teachers are not just implementing curriculum but are actively engaged in continuous improvement and lifelong learning.

Indicators 3 and 4 both obtain the highest mean of 4.50. This showed a strong intrinsic motivation among teachers to upgrade their competencies. As Perusso et al. (2025) highlighted, this proactive engagement in Continuous Professional Development (CPD) is a necessity, not a luxury, maintaining a high instructional quality in rapidly changing educational landscapes. Furthermore, a systematic review by *Frontiers in Education* (2025) confirmed that when teachers actively participate in sustained professional learning would lead to significant positive shifts in their confidence and instructional competence, directly correlating with improved student outcomes.

Table 13 Cognitive Engagement

Indicators	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	f	%	Mean	Interpretation
Actively think of ways to improve teaching practices.	43	32	7	0	0	82	100	4.44	Very High
Contributes ideas during school planning and meetings.	35	42	5	0	0	82	100	4.37	Very High
Engages in professional learning opportunities.	45	33	4	0	0	82	100	4.50	Very High
Seeks opportunities to expand my knowledge and skills.	47	29	6	0	0	82	100	4.50	Very High
Participates in collaborative problem-solving for instructional challenges.	43	34	5	0	0	82	100	4.46	Very High
Overall						82	100	4.45	Very High

Legend:

5 = 4.21-5.00 Very High 2 = 1.81-2.40 Low

4 = 3.61-4.20 High 1 = 1.00-1.80 Very Low

3 = 2.41-3.60 Moderate

On the contrary, though categorized as very high, indicator two recorded the lowest mean among the indicators with only 4.37 implying that while engagement is strong, still it remains a potential to further encourage and institutionalize teacher participation on planning activities. These findings aligned with the research of Andaya & Qunito (2025) on Teacher Leadership Behaviors and Collaborative Practices for Instructional Enhancement, they emphasized that teacher leadership behavior and collaborative practices were essential in improving instructional quality and driving educational success.

Table 14 Emotional Level of Engagement

Indicators	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	f	%	Mean	Interpretation
Feels enthusiastic about participating in school activities.	39	29	12	2	0	82	100	4.28	Very High
Felt a strong sense of belonging in the school community.	38	35	9	0	0	82	100	4.35	Very High
Is emotionally invested in student's success.	45	32	4	1	0	82	100	4.48	Very High
Remained positive and resilient despite the challenges.	39	35	8	0	0	82	100	4.38	Very High
Felt motivated to perform the teaching duties effectively.	38	41	3	0	0	82	100	4.43	Very High
Overall						82	100	4.38	Very High

Legend:

- 5 = 4.21-5.00 Very High 2 = 1.81-2.40 Low
- 4 = 3.61-4.20 High 1 = 1.00-1.80 Very Low
- 3 = 2.41-3.60 Moderate

The results in Table 14 revealed a very high level of emotional engagement among the target respondents with a general weighted mean of 4.38. This showed that educators in the integrated schools were emotionally connected to their profession, highly resilient, and are intensely invested in both the students’ welfare and of the community.

Indicator three showed the highest weighted mean of 4.48, revealing that the most significant driver of this engagement are the respondent’s commitment to the learners. Aligned with the recent educational research, this suggested that “other-oriented” motivations, particularly the desire to impact students’ welfare, were the strongest predictors of teacher satisfaction and efficacy. Studies also emphasized that when teachers demonstrated high emotional competence and investment, this significantly correlated with improved student behavioral and emotional engagement, creating a reciprocal relationship in which student success further motivates the teacher (Frontiers in Psychology, 2025).

Indicator 1, with a weighted mean 4.28, received the lowest score. The variance showed a common professional prioritization where teachers felt a stronger, more immediate emotional connection to their direct work with students than to broader institutional activities. While the strong sense of belonging was a vital positive indicator, research confirms that a teacher’s sense of school membership was linked to trust, job satisfaction, and lower turnover rates, supporting throughout a cohesive educational environment (Behavioral Sciences/ PMC, 2025).

Table 15 indicated that respondents showed a very high level of engagement, with a general weighted mean of 4.28. Results suggested that educators were actively translating their emotional commitment into tangible actions, defining a high level of compliance, innovation, and support from its school community.

The third indicator showed the highest weighted mean of 4.41, highlighting the respondents’ willingness to support the school’s initiative and goals. Research in Frontiers in Psychology confirmed that when teachers actively aligned their behavior with school goals, it created a more cooperative environment and improved overall school performance. While teachers are highly proactive in the classroom, indicator two with a weighted mean of 4.16 received the least result. As studies showed that while highly engaged teachers are eager to innovate for their students, they are also often more hesitant to take on unpaid extra work to protect their energy and avoid burnout (MDPI Behavioral Science, 2023).

Table 15 Behavioral Level of Engagement

Indicators	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	f	%	Mean	Interpretation
School leadership recognized and supported teacher engagement in ancillary activities.	33	36	11	2	0	82	100	4.22	Very High
Volunteers openly for tasks beyond teaching.	27	42	12	1	0	82	100	4.16	High
Supported schools initiatives and goals.	41	34	7	0	0	82	100	4.41	Very High
Implemented new teaching methods or classroom	36	39	5	2	0	82	100	4.33	Very High

activities.									
Engaged in extra activities to supported student learning and school improvement.	38	33	8	3	0	82	100	4.29	Very High
Overall						82	100	4.28	Very High

Legend:

5 = 4.21-5.00 Very High 2 = 1.81-2.40 Low

4 = 3.61-4.20 High 1 = 1.00-1.80 Very Low

3 = 2.41-3.60 Moderate

Finally, the score for Indicator 1 had a weighted mean of 4.22, which highlights the importance of administration. When a leader actively recognizes these efforts, it encourages teachers to keep participating and prevents them from disengaging (MDPI Societies, 2023).

Table 16 Overall Summary of the level of Teacher Engagement

TEACHER ENGAGEMENT	OVERALL MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Cognitive Engagement	4.45	Very High Extent
Emotional Level of Engagement	4.38	Very High Extent
Behavioral Level of Engagement	4.28	Very High Extent

As a summary from the gathered data of the research with regards to level of teacher engagement, revealed that cognitive engagement had the highest among indicators. That provided the research the complete thought that despite the ancillaries, teachers are “all-in”, allowing significant time in planning lesson plans and significant teaching strategies that best fits the learners’ needs. While still on a very high extent, behavioral level of engagement fell the least among three. This domain refers to the observable actions like effort, persistence, and participation in extra-curricular activities as these are also seasonal activities and not in everyday occurrence.

Overall, this study examined the impact of ancillary tasks, defined as the independent variable upon the dependent variable which is the teacher effectiveness and engagement. It revealed that junior high school teachers in the integrated schools execute ancillary duties to a high or very high extent noting that classroom management revealed a weighted mean of 4.23, instructional support with 4.06, and administrative tasks with 3.90 emerging as primary components of their non-instructional workload.

Despite the substantial burden imposed by these responsibilities, respondents consistently demonstrated a very high level of professional effectiveness with weighted mean result between 4.42-4.60, and engagement ranging from 4.28-4.45. this suggested that while ancillary activities constitute a significant professional demand, they are currently managed through a high degree of professional resilience that preserves instructional quality and commitment.

Table 17 Relationship of the Respondents Extent of Ancillary Task and Their Teacher Effectiveness

Variable	r	I	P-value	n	Decision	Remark
Extent of Ancillary Task and Level of Teacher Effectiveness	0.908	High Correlation	0.033	82	Reject H_1	Significant

Level of significance: $\alpha = 0.05$

Degrees of freedom: $df = N - 1 = 81$

Legend:

r = Pearson correlation coefficient

n = number of respondents

p = probability value

I = Interpretation

As shown in Table 17, the correlational test results for the variables indicate that the computed Pearson r value for the relationship between ancillary tasks performed by junior high school teachers of the integrated schools in the division and their teacher effectiveness is 0.908, indicating a high relationship.

The p-value determined the significance of Pearson's r. This was proven by the p-value of 0.033, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). For this reason, the null hypothesis was rejected, which means that there is a significant relationship between the extent of ancillary tasks performed by the junior high school teachers of the integrated schools in the division of San Carlos City and their teachers' effectiveness.

Table 18 Relationship of the Respondents Extent of Ancillary Task and Their Level of Teacher Engagement

Variable	r	I	P-value	n	Decision	Remark
Extent of Ancillary Task and Level of Teacher Engagement	0.960	Very High Correlation	0.010	82	Reject H_2	Significant

Level of significance: $\alpha = 0.05$

Degrees of freedom: $df = N - 1 = 81$

Legend:

r = Pearson correlation coefficient

n = number of respondents

p = probability value

I = Interpretation

Table 18 revealed that the correlation between the extent of ancillary tasks performed by junior high school teachers in integrated schools and their level of teacher engagement was very high, with a Pearson Moment Product Correlation Coefficient of 0.960.

The computation yielded a p-value of 0.10, which is less than the significance level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). For this reason, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means there is a significant relationship between the extent of ancillary tasks performed by junior high school teachers in the Integrated Schools in the division of San Carlos City and their level of teacher engagement. In other words, there is a very high association between the two variables of this study.

CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study was initiated to determine the administrative impact of ancillary activities on the effectiveness and engagement of Junior High School teachers in the Integrated Schools in the Division of San Carlos City. After a thorough evaluation and analysis, the findings were summarized, conclusions were drawn, and recommendations were provided.

Summary of Findings

The study "Administrative Impact of Ancillary Activities on Teacher Effectiveness and Engagement: A Quantitative Inquiry on Junior High School Teachers of Integrated Schools in the Division of San Carlos City" employed a descriptive-correlational design. This particular method is utilized to determine the relationship between two or more variables. In this study, the method is used to profile respondents and assess the extent of ancillary activities and the level of teacher effectiveness. Furthermore, it is correlational as it investigates the significant statistical relationship between the burden of ancillary tasks and the teachers' resulting effectiveness and engagement.

A total of 82 junior high school teachers from the eight Integrated Schools of the division are participating for the 2025-2026 school year. The study consisted of five questions that included the ancillary tasks performed by teachers, teacher effectiveness, and teacher engagement. Each of which contains specific indicators relevant to the research.

The study's purpose was to examine the extent to which ancillary activities are related to teachers' effectiveness and engagement during the 2025-2026 school year. Additionally, this would determine which action plan should be provided to help the teachers ease out of these ancillary activities.

The study measured the extent to which junior high school teachers in Integrated Schools perform ancillary tasks, specifically in administrative duties, classroom management, instructional support, and extracurricular activities.

The result revealed that classroom management performance was excellent, with a weighted mean of 4.23. This implied that regardless of the multiple ancillary responsibilities of teachers, they continue to manage classrooms effectively. Likewise, administrative tasks resulted to a high extent, with a weighted mean of 3.90. Data indicated that teachers, particularly in integrated schools, were equipped to handle such ancillaries, although they represented as additional workloads.

While instructional support tasks seemed to use up teachers' remaining hours and added to their workload, results still showed a strong association of 4.06, revealing that teachers are strongly associated with their professional performance and commitment.

The weighted mean of the data on the extent of teacher effectiveness among junior high school teachers ranges from 4.42 to 4.60, indicating a very high level of teacher effectiveness. These indicate that, despite the heavy ancillary loads, teachers can still achieve positive outcomes in classroom management and instruction, resulting in the desired student learning outcomes.

Additionally, the results for teacher engagement ranged from 4.28 to 4.45, indicating a very great extent. This implies that teacher engagement is closely tied to how these teachers manage their ancillary tasks, given that the analysis was heavily focused on the correlation between these levels and their ancillary workload/s.

The results revealed a significant positive relationship between the variables. The study revealing with a high correlation (Pearson $r = 0.908$) among the extent of ancillary tasks and teacher effectiveness. With the computed p-value of 0.033, this indicated less than the 0.05 significance

level. Such findings resulted in rejecting the null hypothesis, confirming that the ancillary tasks teachers perform were significantly related to their classroom effectiveness.

The study settled with a powerful connection between the additional tasks teachers perform and their level of engagement. From the statistical result of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r) at 0.960, this indicated a very high correlation. Also, the analysis produced a p-value of 0.10, obviously is less than the significance level of 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Therefore, there was a significant relationship between the extent of ancillary tasks performed and the level of teacher engagement. This implies that the two variables are highly associated, meaning the level of engagement, i.e., cognitive, emotional, and behavioral, is strongly tied to the ancillary functions that junior high school teachers in the Integrated Schools fulfill.

Overall, the study concluded that ancillary activities had a profound "administrative impact" on teachers. Despite of teachers maintaining a "very high" level of classroom management, the added workload from administrative and ancillary tasks linked to their overall effectiveness and professional engagement as confirmed by the findings.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Proven administrative impact. Due to the rejection of the null hypotheses on both teacher effectiveness and engagement, confirmed that a statistically significant positive relationship between ancillary activity performance and teacher outcomes. This further conclude that the "administrative impact" were real and profound; while teachers engaged more deeply in school-wide ancillary functions, there were corresponding and measurable increase in their perceived professional effectiveness and engagement levels.

Ancillary tasks: drivers of professional identity. The very high correlation between ancillary tasks and teacher engagement implied that additional responsibilities are not just merely "extra work" but are deeply tied up with the teacher's cognitive, emotional, and behavioral commitment to their field of duty. These roles strengthened their satisfaction to the sense of belonging and professional duty within the Integrated Schools.

Professional resilience. Junior High School teachers in the Integrated Schools of the San Carlos City Division showcased a high level of professional resilience. With the results in administrative and instructional support tasks being rated at a "high extent", they maintained a "very high" level of effectiveness and engagement. This proved that these teachers have developed the capacity to compromise their primary instructional duties in order to facilitate the added workload entrusted to them.

Conjunction between management and instruction. The "very high" extent of classroom management performance indicated that teachers do not see ancillary tasks as isolated burdens. Instead, their mastery in handling the physical and administrative environment of the classroom is fundamentally linked to their overall teaching abilities and success.

Establishment for institutional support. Though the current results were positive, the high workloads indicated that teachers are operating at maximum capacity. The data given served as a critical baseline for school leaders to recognize that maintaining this "very high" level of effectiveness required a structured intervention plan just to ensure that the burden of administrative tasks does not eventually led to burnout or decline in the quality of education.

Recommendations

Along with the findings and conclusions provided, the following recommendations were gathered:

School administrators were encouraged to redistribute and realign the clerical and administrative duties to non-teaching staff, allowing teachers to devote much focus on their line of duties, that is, instructional responsibilities. Guided with structured scheduling, reforms should be implemented to safeguard uninterrupted teaching time and to not compromise the student's learning process. Also, an adequate support systems, such as technological tools and collaborative networks, should be provided to ease and remove the burden of non-instructional tasks.

For **policymakers**, specifically the Department of Education and Local Government Units of San Carlos City, strengthen the enforcement of DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2024, this is to ensure that schools, especially those in remote areas, were staffed with enough non-teaching personnel. Furthermore, it is also a must to allocate resources for support staff and infrastructure, while at the same time establishing monitoring mechanisms in order to regularly assess the impact of these tasks on teacher effectiveness and engagement.

Teachers were advised to engage and participate in professional development programs in order to enhance time management and stress management skills. Teachers in integrated schools, due to their limited numbers, often decline training/seminars under the PD programs with the thought in mind that they would leave learners. At some point, they consider PD programs as a hindrance. For this reason, they as well hinder themselves from acquiring the skills they need to reduce ancillary activities and focus more on classroom engagements.

Future researchers were recommended to conduct comparative studies between private and public schools. This way, they may explore interventions such as digital task management systems and administrative simplification methods. This will enable them to investigate moderating variables, such as teacher tenure, school culture, and leadership practices, and identify practical solutions for mitigating the untoward effects of ancillary tasks.

With these results, the researcher considered the proposed intervention plan to ease teachers' heavy workloads by adding ancillaries. Aligned with the SMART goals and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), the researcher proposed an intervention plan that is actionable and progressive so schools can roll them out in phases.

PROPOSED INTERVENTION PLAN

Source: *Administrative Impact of Ancillary Activities on Teacher Effectiveness and Engagement: A Quantitative Inquiry on Junior High School Teachers of Integrated Schools In the Division of San Carlos City*

Locale: Integrated Schools of SDO- San Carlos City

Cohort: 82 Junior High School Teachers

Intervention Objective:

Establish a sustainable institutional framework that optimizes the management of ancillary tasks through technological integration, administrative support, and policy reform. The plan aims to mitigate workload-related stress and protect the primary instructional role of the teachers, thereby sustaining and enhancing their teaching effectiveness and engagement to perform within and outside the Division. Through this intervention, the administrative impact will divert from a potential "role strain" to becoming a structured and organized, as well as recognized proponent of professional growth ensuring an environment of high academic excellence and teacher satisfaction.

FOCUS AREA	SHORT TERM (0-6 months)	MEDIUM TERM (6-18 months)	LONG TERM (18+ months)
Support for Ancillary Tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assign clerical aides or student assistants; Introduce simple digital tools (e.g. automated forms); Audit workload distribution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop centralized reporting/documentation systems; Train staff on digital platforms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutionalize support staff positions; Fully integrate technology for admin tasks.
	KPI: 20% reduction in time spent for paperwork	KPI: 70% of teachers actively using new systems	KPI: 85-90% satisfaction rate in workload surveys
Teacher Effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct time management workshops; Provide recognition for balancing tasks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Launch PD programs on balancing teaching and ancillary duties; Create mentorship programs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embed ancillary task management into teacher training curricula; Establish incentive systems.
	KPI: 80% workshop participation; 10% in classroom observation scores	KPI: 60% of teachers report improved task management	KPI: sustained “Very High” classroom performance rating over three years
Teacher Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Form peer support groups; Hold consultation sessions for task assignments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implements wellness initiatives (stress management, counseling); Develop collaborative committees. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build shared leadership culture; Regularly evaluate engagement level.
	KPI: 75% teacher participation in support groups	KPI: 15% increase in engagement survey scores	KPI: engagement scores consistently above 85%
Policy and Administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review workload policies; Begin integrating ancillary tasks into evaluations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish clear guidelines for fair task distribution; Conduct semi-annual feedback sessions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formalize balanced workload policies; Institutionalize ancillary contributions in promotion criteria.
	KPI: Policy review completed; 50% of evaluations include ancillary contributions	KPI: 80% of teachers report fair workload distributions	KPI: 100% of promotion reviews include ancillary work
Monitoring and Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up basic tracking of workload vs. performance; Collect teacher feedback surveys. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use data analytics to refine interventions; Publish annual workload/engagement reports. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain continuous monitoring system; Adjusts policies annually based on longitudinal data.

	KPI: 90% survey response rate	KPI: annual reports completed and shared with stakeholders	KPI: Year-on-year improvement in effectiveness and engagement matrix
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Teachers will gain reduce workload stress as they would be less overwhelmed from the excessive paperwork and can focus teaching.

Following this intervention plan, teachers are not just reducing tasks; they are unlocking opportunities for growth, balance, and recognition. Teachers will then be recognized not just as educators in the classroom, but as professionals whose full contributions truly matters.

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